

THE APPLICATION OF ELECTRONIC THEORY TO EXPLAIN ORGANIC REACTIONS AND TO PREDICT OTHERS. PART I. DYES

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The present paper is an attempt at making use of the Electronic Theory as the basis of predicting unknown reactions, and explaining the already known facts and the empirical Nietzke's rule derived therefrom.

An attempt is also made to increase the classes of compounds which couple with diazo compounds. In this respect some preliminary results are given which indicate that the predictions made may not be untrue. A new class of compounds i.e. the acyl amides are predicted to be capable of being diazotised.

It is evident that only electric force can explain the large energy changes involved in chemical reactions. Therefore the fundamental theory of chemistry must be based upon the properties of the electrons. Unfortunately the opinion is generally held that the Electronic Theory, though admirable for purposes of explaining the existing data, cannot be used as a basis for predicting the course of reactions and forecasting unknown reactions. As verification of predictions is the test of a theory, the following work was taken up to remove the above objection. It is hoped to modify the theory if results are obtained contrary to predictions.

Colour and Structure.—OH, NH₂ and Cl are supposed to possess lone pairs of electrons. These electrons are supposed to have the property of conjugation with suitable system of bonds as in aromatic compounds. Thus their influence can easily be transported to *ortho* or *para* position. This conjugation of the lone pair of electrons with the aromatic nucleus facilitates attack on *ortho* and *para* positions by electrophilic reagents. This is the mechanism of the *ortho* and *para* substitution in the benzene series.

In the Theory of Colour and Structure it is found that OH and NH₂ can behave as auxochromes. It is evident that Cl-, Br- and I- are very similar to the above two groups, in having lone pair of electrons conjugated with the aromatic nucleus. If the hypothesis is made that the colour is due to the resonance caused by the conjugation of the lone pair of electrons it becomes evident that:—

(i) Cl-, Br-, I- should also behave as auxochromes.

(ii) As the distance of the nucleus increases from the outer orbit, the auxochromic properties should increase.

(iii) Similarly the auxochromic properties should be NH₂ < NHCH₃ < NHC₂H₅ < N(C₂H₅)₂ as this is the order of the availability of electrons.

Again, in the amide grouping CONH₂

it is found that the compound can assume a form in which the lone pair will have the opportunity of conjugating with the aromatic nucleus.

(iv) Thus CONH₂ group should behave as an auxochromic group.

(v) Similarly CONHOH group should also behave as an auxochrome.

These predictions of behaviour have already been noted. Thus Nietzke's rule is easily explained on the basis of this theory.

(ii) Cl- has got auxochromic properties. Thus dinitrobenzene is colourless while chlorodinitrobenzene is pale yellow, Cl- being a weak auxochrome due to its greater nuclear charge.

(iii) Iodo compounds are more deeply coloured than Br- compounds which are more deeply coloured than the chloro compounds (Nietzke's rule).

(iii) The intensity of the colour increases in the anticipated order: $N(C_2H_5)_2 > NHC_2H_5 > NHCH_3 > NH_3$ (Nietzke's rule).

(iv) $CONH_2$ is well known for enhancing the colour of the azo compounds.

Coupling.—Only six classes of organic compounds are known to couple with diazotised aromatic amines. With the exception of hydrocarbons and compounds containing active methylene group all the other classes of compounds are either phenols and amines or are their derivatives. On similar considerations as above it can be predicted that Cl-, Br-, I-, $CONH_2$ and $CONHOH$ groups when present in the aromatic nucleus of an aromatic compound should lead to its coupling with diazonium salts.

Preliminary experiments performed with *p*-nitraniline show that benzamide, and hydroxamic acids yield deep red dyes. Iodo compounds produce red colour but the dye could not be isolated. Experiments with Cl-, Br- compounds gave inconsistent results.

$COOH$ has the same grouping as $CONH_2$ and should be capable of coupling. Unfortunately however, diazo compounds couple best in alkaline solution when carboxyl group

is present in the form of the resonating structure $C \begin{matrix} \diagup O \\ \diagdown O \end{matrix}$ }—Consequently the resonance hybrid possesses less energy than can be assigned on the basis of the similarity with $CONH_2$ group. Consequently coupling of this group should be difficult. It may, however, be possible where a very strongly coupling diazonium compound acts on the acid under conditions where activation energy is available; e.g. when trinitrobenzene diazonium chloride acts upon benzoic acid in the presence of actinic rays which can be absorbed by $COOH$ group.

$C=S(OH)$, $C=SH$ groups do not suffer from the same defect to an equal extent and hence the coupling of these compounds should be easier.

Iminoethers because they possess the same structure which can relay the lone pair through the conjugated system to the *ortho* and *para* positions should be capable of coupling with diazo compounds. Thus $C_6H_5-C-NH(OEt)$ should couple.

Diazotisation.—Of all the substances aromatic amines are found to diazotise the most easily. This can only be due to the electronic character of the phenyl group attached to the amino group. The electronic character of phenyl groups is quite similar to that of the acyl groups. Thus both aniline and acetamide are weak acids as well as weak bases. Therefore benzamide and other amides should be capable of diazotisation.

The stability of diazonium salts is attributed to the resonance between the structures

Similarly acyl amides can have the resonating structure

Hence the conclusion can be drawn that acyl amides should prove capable of being diazotised and then coupled to phenols. It is known that just as negatively substituted anilines are with difficulty acted upon by nitrous acid, and the diazonium salts give the corresponding phenols with difficulty, similarly the negatively substituted amides show great reluctance in parting with their NH_2 group. In fact the formation of an intermediate stable diazo-compound has been postulated *e.g.* in the case of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{C}_2\text{CONH}_2$ (triphenyl acetamide). Preliminary experiments with benzamide indicate the formation of an azo compound which is not stable.

Work on both the theoretical and practical aspects of the electronic theory is proceeding in these laboratories. Further results of this theoretical approach will be communicated shortly. Experimental verifications of these predictions will be communicated separately when quantitative data are complete.

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